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**SELF EFFICACY AND JOB SATISFACTION OF SECONDARY
SCHOOL TEACHERS**

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Abstract

The present study was undertaken to study the relationship between self efficacy and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers. A sample of 100 teachers from government and private secondary schools of Amritsar district was selected for the purpose of investigation. The findings of the study were: 1) There exists no significant difference in self-efficacy of private and government secondary school teachers. The type of school does not affect the self-efficacy of secondary school teachers. 2) There exists a significant difference in job satisfaction of private and government secondary school teachers. 3) There exists significant relationship between self-efficacy and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers.

Teaching is one of the most significant professions in the world. The result of teaching is that the student is better able to be a valuable and productive citizen. The student learns how to channel energy and creativity in acceptable ways. The student learns how to become an individual who can make her or his way in this world, not becoming a burden on others, but contributing in some measure to the needs of society (Johnson, 2012). As teachers play a special role in setting the standards and creating the conditions for children's school attainments, they are considered to be a key element towards student's academic success. Teachers with high self-efficiency beliefs are more likely to implement innovative methods in the classroom to use classroom management approaches and adequate teaching methods that encourage students' autonomy and reduce custodial control to take responsibility, and to manage classroom problems

than the teachers with a low sense of self-efficiency (Brien, Thombs, Mahoney, & Wallnau, 1994).

Self Efficacy

Self-efficacy as an individual's assessment of his or her ability to cope with given situations (Eysenck, 2000). It is considered as a person's belief about their ability to organize and execute courses of action necessary to achieve a goal. There are some effects of self-efficacy on human behavior. Teachers with high self-efficacy are more motivated than the teachers of low self-efficacy. Low self-efficacy can lead teachers to believe tasks are tough than they actually are. But high self-efficacy helps the teachers to overcome failures by making continuous efforts for completing their goals. In other words, persons with strong efficacy beliefs are more confident in their capacity to execute a behavior (Bandura, 1989). Teacher efficacy as a belief is expected to guide teachers in their behaviors, decisions, and motivation with regard to teaching. The power of self-efficacy is rooted in its ability to guide the decisions that teachers make in the course of their role as teachers.

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a positive or negative evaluative judgment people make about their job. It can be conceptualized as an affective reaction to one's work (Weiss, 2002). It is the desire or un-desire with which employees view their work. It expresses the extent of match between the employer's expectations of the job and rewards that the job provides. It is a product of the working conditions in which a teacher is exposed. Blum(1965) considered job satisfaction as a generalized attitude of the individual resulting for many specific attitudes in three areas namely specific job factors, individual characteristics and group relationship outside the job. These factors are interrelated. In earlier days, the job available to a particular person was often predetermined by the occupation of that person's parents. Nowadays job has great importance in the life of the person who selects his work according to his tastes and likings. There are major changes in his being successful in his profession according to his needs, capabilities and interest.

Significance of the Study

In a developing society, teacher has assumed a great responsibility to bring out good citizens who could carry out the profession in a dignified and productive manner. To achieve their objectives and aspirations, nothing is more important than to secure a sufficient and high quality teaching professions, providing them with best possible professional preparation and to locate for them satisfactory condition of work to make their teaching more effective. Self-efficacy is of great significance for effective functioning of any organization. A strong sense of teacher's self-efficacy promotes a firm commitment to the profession and collaborative relationships with colleagues and parents (Coladarci, 1992; Hoover-Dempsey, Bassler, & Brissie, 1992; Imants & VanZoelen,1995), contributing fruitfully to the promotion of a rich and stimulating learning environment. Job satisfaction influences the employee's performance, enhances productivity of an organization and results in individual self-efficacy. Recent findings have shown that teachers' self-efficacy beliefs have a crucial role in affecting and sustaining their commitment to school and their job satisfaction (Caprara, Barbaranelli, Borgogni, Petitta et al., 2003; Caprara, Barbaranelli, Borgogni, & Steca, 2003. If better services are expected from a teacher and if it is desired to effect and hold better talent in the profession, then there is an immediate need to know the cause of dissatisfaction among teachers and suggest remedies for them. So, teacher's self-efficacy is an issue of nearest as it related to productivity, as a social concerned as an indicator for organizational job commitment.

Hypotheses

1. There exists no significant difference in self-efficacy of private and government secondary school teachers.
2. There exists no significant difference in job satisfaction of private and government secondary school teachers.
3. There exists no significant relation between self-efficacy and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers.

Method and Procedure

Sample

A sample of 100 secondary school teachers was taken from different schools of Amritsar district.

Design

For this purpose ‘Survey’ method was selected as the method of research.

Tools

- 1) Teacher Efficacy Scale (Kumar, 2012)
- 2) Job Satisfaction Scale (Bhatia, Muhir & Mudgil, 1971)

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

Hypothesis I

“There exists no significant difference in self efficacy of private and government secondary school teachers”.

In order to test this hypothesis, Mean and S.D. of self-efficacy scores of private and government of secondary schools teachers were calculated as shown in the table 1:

Table 1: Mean, S.D. and t-value of Self-Efficacy of Private and Government Teachers of Secondary School Teachers

Schools	N	Mean	S.D.	SE _D	t-value
Private	50	64.07	6.11	1.31	0.96
Government	50	65.33	7.02		

The table 1 reveals that the mean score and S.D. of private school teachers is 64.07 and 6.11 respectively and mean score and S.D. of government school teachers is 65.33 and 7.02 respectively. The t-value comes out to be 0.96, which is insignificant at 0.05 and 0.01 levels of confidence. Hence the hypothesis I, “There exists no significant difference in self efficacy of private and government secondary school teachers” is not rejected.

Hypothesis II

“There exists no significant difference in job satisfaction of private and government secondary school teachers”.

In order to test this hypothesis, Mean and S.D. of job satisfaction of private and government secondary schools teachers were calculated. The scores of private and government secondary school teachers have been described in terms of mean, S.D. and t- value in the Table 2

Table 2: Mean, S.D. and t-value of Job Satisfaction of Private and Government Secondary Schools Teachers

Schools	N	Mean	S.D.	SE _D	t-value
Private	50	231.88	29.12	6.15	3.77
Government	50	255.09	32.74		

The table 2 reveals that mean score and S.D. of private school teachers is 231.88 and 29.12 respectively and the mean score and S.D. of government school teachers is 255.09 and 32.75 respectively. The t-value comes out to be 3.77, which is significant at both 0.05 and 0.01 levels of confidence. Hence the hypothesis II, “There exists no significant difference in job satisfaction of private and government secondary school teachers" is rejected. Thus, the job satisfaction of teachers working in government schools is higher than that of the teachers working in private schools.

Hypothesis III

“There exists no significant relationship between self efficacy and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers”.

In order to test this hypothesis, correlation of self-efficacy and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers was calculated. The correlation scores have been described as:

Table 3: Coefficient of Correlation of Self Efficiency and Job Satisfaction of Secondary

School Teachers

Variable	Self Efficacy	Job Satisfaction
Self-Efficacy	–	0.71
Job Satisfaction	0.71	–

The table 3 reveals that coefficient of correlation between self-efficacy and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers comes out to be 0.71, which is significant at both 0.05 and 0.01 levels of confidence. It shows that both the variables are positively correlated. Hence the hypothesis III, ‘There exists no significant relationship between self-efficacy and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers.’ is rejected.

Findings

1. There is no significant difference in self-efficacy of private and government secondary school teachers. Hence, the type of school does not affect the self-efficacy of secondary school teachers.
2. There is a significant difference in job satisfaction of private and government secondary school teachers. Job satisfaction of teachers working in government schools is higher than that of the teachers working in private schools.
3. There is significant relationship between self-efficacy and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers.

Educational Implications

The present study reveals that there is positive relation between self efficacy and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers. So, congenial environment should be created in the schools to enhance job satisfaction which in turn affects self efficacy. In addition to this, it is recommended that seminars or short program of awareness should be conducted to improve the level of self-efficacy of secondary school teachers.

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